

CHEMICAL GRAFTING CNT ONTO CF SURFACE BY ELECTROPHORESIS METHOD

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1 Introduction

Carbon fiber (CF) used to be applied as the reinforcement in the composite materials in recent decades because of its excellent mechanical and electronic properties¹. In order to increase the interfacial shear strength (IFSS), carbon nanotubes (CNT) were often grafted onto the CF surface to improve the combined force between CF and CNT^{2,3}. For the sake of enhancing the grafting density, electronic field was introduced to provide external force to compel CNT flowing to the CF, which is termed electrophoresis method^{4,5}.

However, this method did not improve the IFSS as much as expectation because there is only weak Van der Waals force existing between CF and CNT. In addition, the force was further weakened after the elimination of electricity.

In this paper, we designed a new method which combined electrophoresis and chemical methods. The CNT were force to flow to the CF under electronic field and finally reacted with CF. The chemical bond between CNT and CF greatly increased the IFSS of reinforcement.

2 Experimental

Pretreatment were required for both CF and CNT. CF should be deglued and oxidized, and CNT is also asked for well dispersing in the acetone solvent after oxidization and amination.

Fig. 1 shows the grafting process. The CF and graphite stick were placed into the CNT dispersing solution as two electrode, and 3 mL 1,3-propyldiamine, 0.4 g DCC, 0.4 g DMAP were added into the solution. In addition, 40 mA steady DC was imposed on the two electrode. After 5 hours, the CF was washed by acetone and dried under vacuum for 4 hours.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Surface Topography

Fig. 2 represents the surface topography of CF before and after CNT grafting. Through the grafting, the surface of CF was coated a compact layer of CNT.

3.2 Characteristics

IR spectra of CF were shown in Fig. 3. After reaction, CNT peaks and amide bond peaks were obviously introduced, which confirm that CNT were grafted and amide bond between CNT and CF was generated.

3.3 Mechanical Property

There is an enormous improvement for IFSS of CF after reaction according to the micro-bond test. After oxidization, the IFSS rise from 41.5 MPa to 35.7 MPa because of the slightly damage of conjugated structure of CF surface. When grafting the CNT by electrophoresis method, the IFSS increase to 63.1 MPa, which has 77% and 52% improvement for the oxidized and as-received CF, respectively. The reason of this improvement is that CNT could consume a great portion of energy when the reinforcement were pulled out from matrix when CNT were grafted onto the CF surface.

4 Conclusion

The CNT/CF reinforcement with superhigh grafting density was synthesized by combining electrophoresis and chemical grafting methods. IR spectra confirm that the amide bonds were existed between CF and CNT after grafting. In addition, the IFSS increases 77% after reaction.

Fig.1. Reaction process.

Fig.3. IR spectra of CF reinforcement: (a) before grafting; (b) after grafting.

Fig.2. SEM images of CF: (a) before grafting; (b) after grafting.

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